

INNOVATION IN IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF MUSIC EDUCATION THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: This article discusses the role of the introduction of innovative technologies in the development of music education in the new stage of development of Uzbekistan and the achievement of efficiency in the field. Comparative analyzes of the programs used in teaching the field of music education are also presented.

Key words: informatics, information, music education, music notation writing, program, community information.

INTRODUCTION

Computer tools are increasingly penetrating all aspects of our society shows that the ability to quickly and qualitatively process information becomes a life requirement of every growing young person. The fact that information is becoming a valuable commodity is a sign of the growing influence and importance of computer science[1;3]. Computer tools are increasingly penetrating all aspects of our society shows that the ability to quickly and qualitatively process information becomes a life requirement of every growing young person. The fact that information is becoming a valuable commodity is a sign of the growing influence and importance of computer science[1;3].

Further development of the educational system of higher educational institutions and has the right to selectively develop and implement innovative educational programs that include the latest technologies and teaching methods aimed at improvement. A computer for more active mastering of information technologies it is necessary to improve literacy, including through various programs.

At the end of the 20th century and the beginning of the 21st century, information technologies are spreading widely in almost all spheres of human activity, including the sphere of education. In the field of education, there are processes of computerization, internetization, as well as informationization. As a result of such changes, the quality and efficiency of education and increasing convenience.

The educational process is student-centered learning and student creativity it is characterized by the fact that it is aimed at developing abilities, as well as introducing information and communication technologies into the educational process, creating a single interactive educational information space[2].

RESEARCH RESULTS AND METHODOLOGY

Optimizing the means, forms and methods of teaching music in the form of traditional teaching using new information technologies, finding reasonable solutions to specific educational problems, choosing suitable ways to improve the educational process, and helping to overcome a number of difficulties. appears.

There are following types of computer training programs:

- electronic textbook;
- encyclopedia of electronic music;
- library information-search systems;
- computer programs for knowledge control.

To date, musical computer programs are being developed in the following main areas of music education:

- education of the musician's artistic thinking;
- formation of practical skills;
- development of musical abilities;
- creative activity;
- learning the basic concepts of terms;

Programs typically include game and study sections that explain many musical terms, elements of music literacy and music theory, and quizzes to identify notes and chords.

Programs designed to visually teach the basics of elementary music theory, solfeggio, harmony, and polyphony are aimed at imitating a lesson in one of the theoretical subjects in accordance with the traditional lesson format or developing individual skills that require long term training.

At the same time, the program should conduct a dialogue with the student, receive feedback and evaluate.

Programs aimed at developing hearing skills - intonation, includes various trainings to develop the purity of harmonic, melodic hearing and others.

They have types of auditory dictation that teach recognition of notes, intervals, scales, etc., and practice with graphic fixation of pitch to control the purity of intonation.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Musical literature programs are books, encyclopedias, MIDI files containing a collection of musical works, may include small illustrated guides to various musical works, brief biographies of the relevant composers and musicians, and a small quiz on the material.

The texts of the programs on music literature and music history are illustrated with slides and reproductions, excerpts from musical works, video clips, and selected music and art works and articles may include a narrative along with a slide show.

With the help of such programs, we have students from different countries and periods it allows us to introduce the work of composers, get acquainted with their biography, get information about the music he created, sort some pieces according to notes, get a complete idea about various genres of music, famous singers and musicians, and musical instruments. relief. Hyperlinks allow you to quickly move from one part of the program to another. Programs can be searched by composer, artist name, tag, genre and time period, or a specific topic.

New information technologies are increasingly used in modern music practice and are becoming a part of modern culture. Production of new types of electronic music (synthesizers, music computers) is increasing. The use of multimedia systems in music education includes music encyclopedias, books, reference books, and various materials recorded on laser CDs. allows the use of anthologies for educational purposes.

DISCUSSION

A modern music lesson is a lesson that uses modern pedagogical technologies, computer technologies, and electronic musical instruments. Music lessons are characterized by creating a creative atmosphere, because the content of music lessons consists of emotions and their subjective experience. Such a unique content in different ways, work determines the selection of types and new multimedia tools. Musical computer technologies have opened a completely new stage in the technical reproduction of musical products: in sheet music, applied music genres, sound recording equipment, quality capabilities of sound reproducing equipment, theater and concert activities, sound. design and music broadcasting v.h.

Today, the introduction of new innovative technologies into the process of music education is one of the urgent tasks.

Computer music recording programs can be used not only by teachers and students during the lesson, but also in the process of working on themselves after the lesson, improving performance skills, creating examples of creativity, and using them in practice. Writing and listening to their own works they will have opportunities to conduct creative research on the expressiveness and attractiveness of the works. It is not necessary and impossible to master all the created programs, because mastering them takes a lot of time. I think it is better to use whichever program is convenient in practice.

CONCLUSION

With the help of the "Music Notes Editor" program, it is possible to create notational and vocal tests from all subjects related to music education. These visual and audio tests improve the quality of assessment of learners' knowledge, listening and analytical skills and competencies.

In conclusion, it can be said that the use of new innovative technologies in the process of music education, the popularization of the scientific and practical results of working in the musical notation program as a teaching and methodical guide is an urgent issue. remains.

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